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D2.2 Guidelines on interoperability for multi-Ris services addressing the agro- ecological transition

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Executive Summary

This document *D2.2 – Guidelines on interoperability for multiRis services addressing the agro-ecological transition* establishes the framework under which the AgroServ consortium will approach interoperability in scientific and technical processes during the project's activities, including the implementation of transnational and virtual access projects.

The need for an interoperable framework arises from the Horizon Europe INFRASERV funding scheme offers integrating services from multiple European research infrastructures (RIs) under a unified initiative, with the aim to addressing significantly urgent challenges. The AgroServ project brings together a wide range of interdisciplinary and international facilities from 12 pan-European infrastructures in life, food, and environmental sciences, each with its distinct research culture and operational routines, to provide the necessary services with the objective to address the pressing needs in the agroecological transition. These collaborating facilities then face the task of aligning their varied practices within a standardized operational environment across the 12 Research Infrastructures within this framework as a collaboration. In this context of multidisciplinary multi-Ris services provision, enabling interoperability is a fundamental need and has already been undertaken in the project with the development of the AgroServ catalogue of services, that links existing catalogues, and is standardised to EOSC requirements.

This document sets the stage, defines issues and develops potential pathways to interoperability needs that unfold in several layers, from scientific interoperability to technical interoperability and standardized management vocabulary.

Scientific interoperability: Semantic interoperability is a core requirement to make data FAIR (Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable). AgroServ's partners will need to provide commitment, and a considerable effort, to converge on a compatible disciplinary vocabulary. Additionally, there is a need to use an appropriate standard **data format**, which will allow data and metadata to be compatible with the software tools and machines. This living document will provide a framework to facilitate this convergence.

Technical interoperability: consists of providing a framework of principles and the methodologies of services provision. This work must be done in accordance with the European Charter for Access to RIs where applicable.

Organisational interoperability: A standardized organisational vocabulary is proposed to facilitate interoperability of managerial aspects of AgroServ project.

Finally, we describe how these interoperability guidelines will be revisited and updated during the project duration until 2027.

The current document represents the first version of the guidelines on interoperability thus containing preliminary information and frameworks that will be adhered to, and potentially revised, with a view to enhancing and characterizing the project's interoperability framework (which will be presented in subsequent iterations of this deliverable).

Introduction

This document establishes the scientific and technical interoperability guidelines for the AgroServ (Integrated SERvices supporting a sustainable AGROecological transition) project, which aims to support sustainable agroecological transitions through its integrated service offer from the 12 Research Infrastructures in the project. It details the *interoperable* approaches, principles, and best practices essential for various aspects of the planned project activities.

The need for interoperability guidelines stems from the fact that AgroServ as a project supported within the scope of the INFRASERV funding scheme represents an initiative that has brought a variety of European research infrastructures (RIs)¹ under one umbrella for the purpose of providing an integrated service offer required to address the challenges of agroecological transitions.

Integrated Service Offer: This network consists of a variety of interdisciplinary and international facilities that have, over the years, developed their own research practices and working routines adapted to their specific scientific field, and are currently embracing the challenge of operating within an environment of standardized practices. The INFRASERV scheme was launched as part of the Horizon Europe program to tackle major challenges and priorities by integrating pan-European research infrastructures around themes chosen to address urgent (societal and scientific) concerns. The primary goal of the projects supported under this scheme is to offer researchers, and other users, a wide-ranging interdisciplinary catalogue of services from the participating research infrastructures (RIs). Additionally, the scheme has an internal function: it encourages collaboration among large infrastructures through thematic networks, creating platforms for sharing best practices in service provision and scientific knowledge creation. As such, this approach not only fosters interdisciplinary collaboration across infrastructures but also creates the new challenge of accommodating different infrastructural practices within a single platform.

AgroServ collaborations and Integrated service offer: The AgroServ consortium as one of the beneficiaries of the INFRASERV scheme includes RIs from the life, food, and environmental sciences and focuses on achieving sustainable and resilient agriculture by promoting agroecological transitions. Consisting of 11 RIs, the consortium provides more than 140 different services in a collective [catalogue](#) to address this challenge under the AgroServ umbrella². However, merging the unique routines, practices, and ideas of these 11 RIs into one platform presents a challenge of compatibility. To ensure seamless cooperation towards a common goal, the partners have proposed several measures to address these compatibility issues and facilitate effective collaboration that will be described in detail in the following sections. Among these, a set of guidelines for *interoperability* constitutes the basis of this deliverable. As described in the AgroServ description of work, these guidelines will address four of interoperability, i.e.,

- scientific domains,
- technical (service provision),
- data management, and
- organisational practices.

¹ The RIs in the AGROSERV consortium are listed in the Annex I. List of AgroServ research infrastructures.

² AgroServ provides researchers with access to 143 research installations that support experiments aimed at both fundamental and applied aspects of sustainable, resilient agriculture and agroecological transitions. Researchers can use these facilities to explore a wide range of questions, including simulations of current and future climate conditions, testing new management strategies, and evaluating crop performance under variable conditions. These services and facilities offer means for experimentation, analysis, and observation. They provide both virtual and physical tools essential for conducting basic and applied research.

<https://isia.cnrs.fr/catalog/service/list/agroserv>

For each layer, problems and needs are identified and strategic suggestions have been presented in this document. These should be considered in the ongoing development and deployment of the AgroServ project elements. These suggestions and proposals were formulated following a thorough examination of relevant EC funded project deliverables and through personal consultations with service providers and project Deliverables.

Scope and objectives

The task of defining interoperability presents an initial challenge that is described below. It is mainly understood in the context of "research data" under the FAIR principles³. It indicates "the ability of data or tools from non-cooperating resources to integrate or work together with minimal effort with applications or workflows dedicated to analysis, storage, and processing."⁴ However, as previously described, interoperability is applicable in a much larger context than data, and in the framework of AgroServ's objectives, it encompasses various operational facets, including scientific domains and sub-domains, scientific output, service workflows and protocols, etc. Therefore, this document endeavours to address interoperability across these spheres—scientific domains, technical service provision, data management, and organisational practices— and emphasizing the necessity for seamless integration and operational harmony within the AGROSERV project. As such, it does not impose specific actions or terminology for partners to adopt or follow, but rather provides a general framework for understanding the varied scientific frameworks within which partners work and establishes guidelines for exchange and mutual learning.

The current deliverable D2.2 – *Guidelines on interoperability for multi-Ris services addressing the agro-ecological transition* – serves as a guideline adhering to European references on the development, application, integration, and maintenance of interoperability standards during the AgroServ project and beyond its conclusion, with updates scheduled for Month 30 and 42. It facilitates consortium-wide consistency in the project's approaches and practices. The objective is to promote the definitions and approach brought forward in the following documents:

- **EOSC Interoperability Framework:** The EOSC Interoperability Framework is a set of policies and guidelines (e.g., documents, procedures, workflows, scripts, code, datasets, formats) that enable interoperability of resources and services, and will facilitate service composability.
- **European Charter for Access to RIS:** This document sets out non-regulatory principles and guidelines to be used as a reference when defining Access policies for Research Infrastructures and related services.
- **ESFRI Report on Access to Research Infrastructures and Charter on Access to RIs:** This report presents the findings and recommendations of the ESFRI Drafting Group on Access, focusing on identifying challenges to, and proposing enhancements for, broader and more effective access to research infrastructures within the European Research Area, as part of the ERA Policy Agenda 2022-2024 Action 8

³ The acronym FAIR stands for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.
<https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-make-your-data-fair>

⁴ Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Sci Data* **3**, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Additionally, D2.2 will build on the previous AgroServ work summarised and published in the following deliverables:

- **D2.1 Catalogue of Services:** This report outlines the progress and developments of Task 2.1 in AgroServ, aimed at creating an online catalogue to enhance the visibility and accessibility of customised services and resources for Transnational Access projects.
- **D9.4 AGROSERV Research Data Management plan:** The present deliverable D9.4 – Data Management Plan – establishes the framework under which Agro-Serv consortium will generate, process and collect data during project’s activities including the implementation of TNA projects.
- **D1.3 AGROSERV Access Policy:** This document outlines the AgroServ Access Policy, which sets the framework for regulating access to AgroServ’s research infrastructures, resources, and services.

While AgroServ may not directly manage all interoperability aspects, this document sets forth a series of guidelines and best practices that individual infrastructures are expected to follow in their TA/VA and remote access projects, producing research outputs and managing their data aggregation.

Finally, given the dynamic and continuously evolving nature of scientific research and technical standards, this document will be appended, or modified to incorporate new best practices as they emerge. Thus, establishing a framework for managing these changes is crucial.

Relation to other activities

As with other WP2 (“Integration and customisation of services”) deliverables, D2.2 will have a broad impact throughout AgroServ, offering guidance on how partners should develop, apply, integrate, and maintain interoperability standards during all activities conducted within, and beyond, AgroServ.

The Guidelines will be made publicly available to ensure that the entire consortium is informed of the practices to be adhered to during these activities. Facility representatives who are tasked with coordinating the access campaigns are expected to review this document and assess the compatibility of their policies and practices to the policies outlined herein when planning their project activities.

Potential future revisions

AgroServ participants recognize how the scientific and technical environment is continuously evolving, with technologies and new inter-/transdisciplinary approaches rapidly becoming not just an enabler, but a critical component of research. Given that standards, approaches, and best practices may shift during the 60 months duration of the AgroServ project, we acknowledge the potential need for updates to interoperability guidelines over the project’s duration, highlighting the importance of an effective change management framework.

The Interoperability Guidelines will undergo two scheduled revisions⁵, during which an interoperability focus group from WP1 Integrated joint management framework for TNA and WP2 AgroServ

⁵ See Annex II for more information regarding the revision timeline.

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integration and customization of services will be established to implement the following steps in a timely manner:

Identification of change requests: in the event of new interoperability needs identified by consortium members, the above referred focus group will determine which parts of the current document are affected by the changing standards, assess the urgency and feasibility of their implementation within the scheduled updates.

Guidelines change specification: for each change request, the committee will develop new and appropriate procedures and draft a candidate revision of the Interoperability Guidelines.

AgroServ identifies the EU, the ESFRI community, the EOSC association, and relevant projects funded under the INFRAEOSC initiative⁶ as reference sources of interoperability standards. The Interoperability Guidelines are expected to be revised by M30 and M42, respectively.

⁶ See [Fostering FAIR Data Practices in Europe](#) (FAIR4FAIR), [OpenAIRE-Nexus Scholarly Communication Services for EOSC users](#) (OpenAIRE Nexus), [Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud](#) (SSHOC), [ENVironmental Research Infrastructures building Fair services Accessible for society, Innovation and Research](#) (ENVRI-FAIR)

Scientific interoperability

It is already established that interdisciplinarity is a core characteristic of AgroServ. The initiative's diverse service offer is designed to support the agroecological transitions. To this end, AgroServ will facilitate user-led experiments—be they transnational or virtual—throughout the project's duration, to yield valuable research outputs.

While mobilizing researchers from all parts of the world for these collaborative experiments, AgroServ will facilitate countless encounters between researchers who bring together ideas built upon their specific scientific backgrounds. The result of these encounters will broaden the horizon for new knowledge creation. However, it also presents new challenges, particularly in organizing the classification of this scientific output. The AgroServ consortium believes that the existing classifications of domains and subdomains serve as a useful starting point. Yet, as the production of interdisciplinary output increases, the currently identified sub-domains specific to agroecology will need to be further refined, or even re-defined, to facilitate interoperability.

First, we address the subject of interoperability concerning the *categorisation* of scientific domains and sub domains, which will be used to categorize the research that will be facilitated through AgroServ. Secondly, data and metadata interoperability will be framed in line with the AgroServ Data Management Plan (D9.4).

Semantic interoperability: Scientific sub-/domains and agroecological transition

In this section, we address the classification of scientific domains and subdomains, explaining our rationale for the chosen categorization within the AgroServ catalogue.

AgroServ provides a unique opportunity in bringing together 11 RIs from different domains, and with diverse technological skills, working towards a common goal. It has a key role to play in this context, to propose a common syntax to complement, or provide a more fine-grained view, of the existing classification provided by EOSC, which in fact seems to be too broad in the case of subdomains in agricultural sciences. The AgroServ consortium is well placed to suggest improvements, especially in pinpointing subdomains that might need to be included or refined / subdivided to improve the current classification.

To this end, the AgroServ project has originally compiled a list of scientific research domains and subdomains from their infrastructures, as documented in the Table 9 Services/Resources Scientific Domain Classification of [D2.1 Catalogue of Services](#). That extensive list has been a reference as it accommodates the input provided by all participating infrastructures however several measures were needed to be implemented for an improved interoperability. At this stage, our effort focused on refining the initial list of domains and subdomains as they were presented in the above table with a view to aligning the existent list of domains with the EOSC classification. Therefore, as a starting point we have adopted the EOSC list of domains and subdomains⁷ (Annex III) which provides a basis for future improvements.

⁷ EOSC follows the Eurostat standard code list for the classification of fields of science and technology. This list originated from the revised field of science and technology classification (FOS 2007), included in the FRASCATI manual (2015)7,8. This work was done by OECD members, in collaboration with the UNESCO and it is widely used around the

The AgroServ project is still in its early stages and such attempts towards multilevel classification and/or the definition of new categories of sub-domains will take place according to a pre-designated pathway of action. A comprehensive classification and definition of new interdisciplinary sub-domains will build on the results of the interoperability focus group meetings after the implementation of the rounds of access projects.

The following strategy will be implemented in two rounds according to the revision table as presented in the Annex I: Revision timeline of the D2.2 Guidelines on interoperability for multiRis services addressing the agro-ecological transition :

- 1) Identification of the domains and subdomains linked to AgroServ topics based on the refinement of the EOSC list (**see Annex III for the current version**). The purpose of the current list (Annex III) is to establish a basic classification to be used in the categorization of outputs after until the next revision and finally serve as a foundation for recommendations and implementation. The proposals for modification will be harmonised with the current definitions of domains and subdomains, enhancing what is already established. The work of the focus will be aligned with the revised timetable of this deliverable.
- 2) Meetings of the interoperability focus group tasked with revising the list, potentially generating new interdisciplinary sub-domains, and recommending possible modifications to the EOSC. The focus group will consist of representatives from the WP1 Integrated joint management framework for TAVA, and WP2 AgroServ integration and customization of services.

When established, this list of suggestions will be shared with EOSC to serve as a base of discussion during the next iteration of the FOS list or the FRASCATI manual. It should be noted that this engagement will be facilitated by the strong involvement of some AgroServ partner infrastructures with the EOSC initiative, including but not limited to ELIXIR, EuroBioImaging and LifeWatch. This objective is clearly beyond the lifetime of the AgroServ project but will constitute an important legacy over the long-term.

Data and Meta Data compability

The Agro-Serv consortium emphasizes the critical role of data and metadata compatibility for enhancing data interoperability within the community, as detailed in our Data Management Plan (DMP). Should a data asset lack the capability for comparison, merging, or integration with other assets, its publication would subsequently offer minimal value to the broader community. This section, adapted from Deliverable [D9.4 Data Management Plan \(DMP\)](#) underlines the importance of adhering to best practices in data management to ensure the maximum utility of data assets within our field. Without imposing strict pathways and rules to be complied with by the partners, this section of the guidelines encourages data interoperability standards and highlights various key areas to ensure effective data usage and integration as outlined below:

- **Data Interoperability Commitment:** the AgroServ project is dedicated to ensuring that data assets can be effectively compared by the partners, merged, or integrated with others, recognizing this as essential for community value.

world. The decision to use EOSC is aimed at enabling the interoperability of the AgroServ catalogue with other service and service provider catalogues across Europe and globally.

- **Documentation Importance:** Documentation of research data assets is vital for interoperability. While specific documentation standards are not enforced, adherence to approved repository best practices is required. Documentation must be public, easily navigable, and enriched with hypertext links, preferably in formats like markdown, HTML, or similar markup languages.
- **Metadata Formats and Vocabularies:** Research data assets must have appropriate domain-specific metadata for integration with third-party assets. Though specific formats are not enforced, the use of FAIRsharing listed vocabularies and adherence to host repository best practices are encouraged. Acceptable domain specific metadata formats and vocabularies are listed in FAIRsharing, their use is described in [RDMkit](#) and the [FAIR Cookbook](#). See [D9.4 AGROSERV Research Data Management plan](#).
- **Controlled Vocabulary Assistance:** The use of controlled vocabulary from thesauri, linked with unique identifiers (URIs), is crucial for interoperability and visibility. A tool is provided within the Data Management Plan to assist with thesaurus term suggestions.
- **Data Formats and Conventions:** TNA beneficiaries must use machine-readable formats for data assets, with no specific formats mandated if the data is hosted on Acceptable Repositories and follows the host's best practices. Examples of acceptable formats include but are not limited to the ones presented in the following table.

Data type	Suggested format
Tabular data	CSV, international format without comments
Semi-structured data	JSON, XML
Raster grids	NetCDF, GeoTIFF
Vector geographic data	shapefile, GeoJSON, WKT
Textual data	TXT, unicode encoding

As the project progresses, the strategies and standards for data interoperability and management outlined in this document will evolve in alignment with advancements and insights from WP3 *Consolidating integrated data management and analysis services*. We will continuously monitor developments within WP3 to ensure that future versions of this document reflect the most current practices in research data management and interoperability, adapting as necessary to meet the emerging needs and challenges of our community.

Technical Interoperability: good practices and methodologies of service provision

This section aims to support the AGROSERV project in its goal of enhancing broader and more effective access to its integrated service offer. It highlights the need for implementing suitable interoperability measures as part of the Transnational Access, Remote Access, and Virtual Access projects. To achieve the AGROSERV project's technical interoperability goals and ensure comprehensive and effective access for all stakeholders, it is crucial to develop a shared understanding of various access-related aspects, including access policies, data management, and legal issues. Our main objective is to offer more standardized and interoperable access while removing potential misinterpretations regarding access provision. The suggestions are informed by feedback from the experience of facilities/installations and users and applicants.

To facilitate comparison and establish common, interoperable, practices, the below check list with questions about generally accepted good practices of access, has been created. This list also has the added advantage of raising the awareness of access providers aware about standard (references for) good practices.

Check box for methodologies and practices of access provision

Theme	Question	
I. Nature of access	1. Has your facility adopted the basic definitions as provided in the European Charter for Access to RIS ?	<input type="checkbox"/>
	2. Has your facility specified and prepared the technical infrastructure for the types of access to be provided (TA, VA, RA)?	<input type="checkbox"/>
	3. Has your facility specified its core offers as outlined in the ESFRI Report on Access to Research Infrastructures and Charter on Access to RIs (below) and corresponding services? Note: Primary examples include but are not limited to:	<input type="checkbox"/>
	machine time	<input type="checkbox"/>
	setting up experiments	<input type="checkbox"/>
	expert support	<input type="checkbox"/>

	training	<input type="checkbox"/>
	access to data	<input type="checkbox"/>
	analytical services	<input type="checkbox"/>
	access to archives	<input type="checkbox"/>
II. General policy for access provision	4. Has your facility adopted and published an access policy that regulates how the access will be provided (in line with the D1.3 AGROSERV Access Policy)?	<input type="checkbox"/>
III. Pre-access	5. Has your facility adopted a Hosting Agreement that defines the purpose of hosting External Users' staff on the premises of the Parties, among other elements, including relevant intellectual property rules? Note: The conditions of confidentiality, publication and communication shall be expressly mentioned in any of the above-mentioned specific agreements signed between the External Users and the concerned Parties.	<input type="checkbox"/>
	5. Has your facility adopted a License Agreement requiring prior approval from the owning Party/ies for all access rights to the Background and Results of the Parties?	<input type="checkbox"/>
	6. Has your facility adopted and announced a GDPR 2016/679 compliant policy for the protection of personal data specifying how the personal data of the natural persons involved in the access process will be processed, stored, and disseminated?	<input type="checkbox"/>

<p>IV. During the access campaign</p>	<p>7. As a condition for funding, has your facility committed to providing a report of completion on the conducted experiment and its results? Note: Each TA user/user group granted access to an AGROSERV infrastructure is committed to providing to the AGROSERV RI manager This report will be communicated to the EU and will enable the users to benefit from AGROSERV's promotion through the project's communication tools (newsletter, website, etc.).</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/></p>
	<p>8. Has your facility adopted a data management plan in compliant with the D9.4 AGROSERV Research Data Management plan?</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>V. Post-access</p>	<p>9. Has your facility adopted a dissemination process for the results of TNA projects? Note: This practice is compulsory for TA users, except for those employed by SMEs. This dissemination may be postponed until an investigation into IP issues is completed. Results can be disseminated by uploading the data to the project database or through a scientific publication.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/></p>

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Standardized organizational vocabulary

This section lays down an initial organisational vocabulary with a view to standardize the terms to describe aspects such as platforms, services, resources, and experiments across various RIs. The initial discussions leading up to the establishment of the first transnational access call underscored the challenge posed by the wide variety of practices and terminology which were used by individual infrastructures of the AgroServ consortium. For example, there is an interchangeable use of research techniques and the material infrastructures i.e., some facility representatives used the term installation while others preferred infrastructure or service as an input to the AgroServ catalogue. This confusion and lack of a standard vocabulary poses a challenge to interoperability, which necessitates a uniform management vocabulary across different aspects of RI management, and crucially this confusion is relayed to the user directly or indirectly and strongly impedes their (proper) use of the service offer.

To address this issue, the first step is to compile a comprehensive inventory of the necessary vocabulary and the existing definitions. Given that the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) already employs a standardized organisational vocabulary that is compatible with the ESFRI vocabulary for RIs, it is recommended to begin by cataloguing the vocabulary utilized within EOSC (refer to Annex IV).

Subsequently, a WP1/WP2 interoperability focus group will collaborate to assess the usefulness of the proposed terminology and share insights with the aim of aligning the vocabulary used within each RI. This process will involve suggesting vocabulary and definitions that are currently not covered by EOSC. The goal is to integrate this harmonized vocabulary and definitions into the ISIA platform, as well as to contribute to the enhancement of the vocabulary at the EOSC level. This will bolster interoperability between the ISIA catalogue and the EOSC catalogue, thereby facilitating more seamless integration across different scientific fields.

This will ideally foster interoperability among various INFRASERV projects and thereby contribute to a meta-interoperability framework for the pan-European RIs.

Annex I: AgroServ Infrastructures

ERIC/RI	Field description	Domain	Subdomain
LifeWatch	Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research	Natural Sciences	Biological Sciences
EMBRC	Marine Biology Ressources	Natural Sciences / Agricultural Sciences	Biological Sciences/Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries
EU-OPENSREEN	Chemical Biology	Natural Sciences / Agricultural Sciences	Biological Sciences/ Agricultural Biotechnology
Euro-Biolmaging	Biology and Biomedical Sciences	Natural Sciences	Biological Sciences
ANAEE	Ecosystems	Natural Sciences / Agricultural Sciences	Biological Sciences/Agriculture, Forestry, Fisheries
MIRRI	Microbiology	Natural Sciences	Biological Sciences
ELIXIR	Sequencing Life Science	Natural Sciences / Agricultural Sciences	Biological Sciences / Agricultural Biotechnology
Emphasis	Plant Phenotyping	Natural Sciences / Engineering & Technologies	Biological Sciences / Industrial Biotechnology
IBISBA	Biotechnology and Biomanufacturing	Engineering & Technologies / Agricultural Sciences	Chemical Engineering / Agricultural Biotechnology
METROFOOD	Metrology in food and nutrition	Engineering & Technologies	Other engineering and technologies
SmartCow	Innovation in the European Cattle Sector	Agricultural Sciences	Animal & Dairy Science

Annex II: Revision timeline of the D2.2 Guidelines on interoperability for multiRis services addressing the agro-ecological transition

Action	Timeline
Planned Data Management Plan update	M24
First identification of change requests	M27
First revision to the D2.2.	M30
Planned Data Management Plan update	M36
First identification of change requests	M39
Final revisions to the D2.2.	M42

Annex III Current List of domains and sub domains on EOSC

Scientific Domain	Scientific Subdomain	3 rd level
Natural Sciences	Mathematics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pure mathematics, applied mathematics, statistics and probability.
	Computer and information sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Computer sciences, information science and bioinformatics
	Physical sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Atomic, molecular and chemical physics, Condensed matter physics, Particles and fields physics, Nuclear physics, Fluids and plasma physics, Optics, Acoustics, Astronomy.
	Chemical sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic chemistry, Inorganic and nuclear chemistry, Physical chemistry, Polymer science, Electrochemistry, Colloid chemistry, Analytical chemistry.
	Earth and related Environmental sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Geosciences, Mineralogy, Paleontology, Geochemistry and geophysics, Physical geography, Geology, Volcanology, Environmental sciences, Meteorology and atmospheric sciences, climatic research.
	Biological sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cell biology, Microbiology, Virology, Biochemistry and molecular biology, Biochemical research methods, Mycology, Biophysics. Genetics and heredity, Reproductive biology, Developmental biology Plant sciences, botany Zoology, Ornithology, Entomology, Behavioural sciences biology Marine biology, Freshwater biology, Limnology, Ecology, Biodiversity conservation. Biology (theoretical, mathematical, thermal, crybiology, biological rhythm), Evolutionary biology, other biological topics
	Other natural sciences	
Engineering & Technology	Civil Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Civil engineering, Architecture engineering, Construction engineering, Municipal and structure engineering, Transport engineering.

	Electrical, Electronic & Information Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electrical and electronic engineering, Robotics and automatic control, Automation and control system, Communication engineering and systems, Telecommunications, Computer hardware and architecture.
	Mechanical Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mechanical engineering, Applied mechanics, Thermodynamics. Aerospace engineering Nuclear related engineering Audio engineering, reliability analysis
	Chemical Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chemical engineering (plants, products), Chemical process engineering
	Materials Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Materials engineering, Ceramics, Coating and films, Composites, Paper and wood, Textiles
	Medical Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Medical Engineering, Medical laboratory technology
	Environmental Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Environmental biotechnology, Bioremediation, diagnostic biotechnologies in environmental management, Environmental biotechnology related ethics
	Industrial Biotechnology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industrial biotechnology, Bioprocessing technologies, Biocatalysis, Fermentation, Bioproducts, Biomaterials, Bioplastics, Biofuels, Bio-derived bulk and fine chemicals, Bio-derived novel materials
	Nano-technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nano-materials Nano-processes
	Other engineering and technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Food and beverages Other engineering and technologies
Agricultural Sciences	Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agriculture, Forestry, Fishery, Soil Science, Horticulture, Viticulture, Agronomy, Plant breeding and protection
	Animal and Dairy science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Animal and dairy science Husbandry, Pets
	Agricultural biotechnology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Agricultural biotechnology and food biotechnology, GM technology (crops and livestock), Livestock cloning, Marker assisted selection, Diagnostics, Biomass feedstock production technologies, Biopharming, Agricultural biotechnology related ethics
	Other agricultural sciences	

Social sciences	Psychology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psychology • Psychology, special
	Economics and Business	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economics, Econometrics, Industrial relations • Business and Management
	Educational sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Education, general • Education, special
	Sociology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sociology, Demography, Anthropology, Ethnology • Social topics
	Law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Law, Criminology, Penology
	Political science	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political science, Public administration, Organisation theory
	Social and Economic Geography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental sciences (social aspects, Cultural and economic geography, Urban studies (Planning and Development), Transport planning and social aspects of transport
	Media and Communications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journalism, Information science (social aspects), Library science, Media and socio-cultural communication
	Other social sciences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social sciences, interdisciplinary • Other social sciences

Annex IV: Standardized organisational vocabulary

- **Portal**

AGROSERV Portal: The Portal providing information about Research Infrastructure Services and Resources offered by AGROSERV providers.

AGROSERV Service or Resource: The AGROSERV Portal will be offering services among which are lists and classifications of services and resources, information about the relevant service and resource providers, advanced search options, filtering and visualisation functionalities, etc.

Portal End-User: Individual that primarily benefits from and uses a Portal.

Portal Operator: The organisation responsible for supplying one or more components of a Portal.

- **Research Infrastructure**

Accessibility of information: Property of information being accessible and usable by an authorized party.

Assessment: Set of actions to evaluate the capability level of a process or the overall maturity level of a management system.

Classification: Assignment of items to defined groups based on common attributes, relations or other criteria¹.

Management review: Periodic evaluation of the suitability, maturity and efficiency of the entire management system by its accountable owner(s), from which opportunities for improvement are identified and follow-up actions are determined².

Management system: Entirety of policies, processes, procedures and related resources and capabilities aiming at effectively performing management tasks in a given context and for a given subject³.

Maturity level: Achieved overall effectiveness of a service and resource management system, based on the combination of the capability levels of its processes and general aspects of management.

Information security: Preservation of confidentiality, integrity and accessibility of information.

Information security control: Means of controlling or treating one or more risks to information security.

Information security event: Occurrence or previously unknown situation indicating a possible breach of information security⁴.

Information security incident: Single information security event or a series of information security events with a significant probability of having a negative impact on the delivery of service and resources to customers, and therefore on the customers' business operations.

Integrity of information: Property of information not being subject to unauthorized modification,

duplication or deletion.

Operational level agreement (OLA): Documented agreement between a provider and another part of the provider's organisation or a federation member to provide a service and resource component or subsidiary service and resource needed to allow provision of service and resources to customers.

Policy: Documented set of intentions, expectations, goals, rules and requirements, often formally expressed by top management representatives in an organisation or federation⁵.

Supplier: External organisation that provides a (supporting) service and resource or service and resource component(s) to the service and resource provider, which they need in order to provide service and resources to their customers/users.

- **Research Services**

Availability: Ability of a service and resource or service and resource component to fulfil its intended function at a specific time or over a specific period of time.

Continuity: Property of a service to maintain all or parts of its functionality, even in exceptional circumstances⁶.

Improvement: Action or set of actions carried out to increase the level of conformity, effectiveness or efficiency of a management system, process or activity, or to increase the quality or performance of a service and resource or service and resource component⁷.

Incident: Unplanned disruption of operation in a service and resource or service and resource component, or degradation of service and resource quality versus the expected or agreed service and resource level or operational level according to service and resource level agreements (SLAs), operational level agreements (OLAs) and underpinning agreements (UAs).

IT service and resource: Service and resource that is enabled by the use of information technology (IT).

IT service management (ITSM): Entirety of activities performed by an IT service and resource provider to plan, deliver, operate and control IT service and resources offered to customers⁸.

Key performance indicator (KPI): Metric that is used to track the performance, effectiveness or efficiency of a service and resource or process⁹.

Operational target: Reference/target value for a parameter used to measure the performance of a service and resource component, listed in an operational level agreement (OLA) or underpinning agreement (UA) related to this service and resource component¹⁰.

Physical RI Service and resource: RI Services and Resources that rely on the access to or use of a physical facility or instrument.

Procedure: Specified set of steps or instructions to be carried out by an individual or group to perform one or more activities of a process.

Process: Structured set of activities, with clearly defined responsibilities, that bring about a specific

objective or set of results from a set of defined inputs¹¹.

Related Platforms: List of suites or thematic platforms in which the service and resource is engaged or providers (provider groups) contributing to this service are engaged.

Related Services: List of other services and resources that are commonly used with a specific service and resource.

Required Services: List of other services and resources required with this service and resource.

Resource: Any physical or digital asset or infrastructure made available to users and customers¹².

Risk: Possible negative occurrence that would have a negative impact on the service and resource provider's ability to deliver agreed service and resources to customers, or that would decrease the value generated through some service and resource¹³.

RI Service and resource: Services and resources provided by Research Infrastructures. They include among others access to and use of facilities and instruments, users support and training and other activities and resources that the RIs deliver to Users/Customers.

Service: The means or a process that organisations use to deliver results that users/customers value and wish to achieve. These results are usually intangible although they may also include tangible elements. Services require instantiation by a Service Provider. Services include networking, compute, data & material storage, training, consultancy, etc¹⁴.

Service component: Logical part of a service that provides a function enabling or enhancing a service¹⁵.

Service and resource acceptance criteria (SAC): Criteria that must be fulfilled by the time a new or changed service and resource is deployed and made available to customers/users¹⁶.

Service and resource catalogue: Customer-facing list of all live services and resources offered along with relevant information about these service and resources¹⁷.

Service and resource component: Logical part of a service and resource that provides a function enabling or enhancing a service and resource¹⁸.

Service and resource Change Log: Summary of the service and resource features updated from the previous version.

Service and resource design and transition package (SDTP): Entirety of plans for the design and transition of a specific new or changed service and resource¹⁹.

Service and resource level agreement (SLA): Documented agreement between a customer and service and resource provider that specifies the service and resource to be provided and the service and resource targets that define how it will be provided.

Service management: Entirety of activities performed by a service provider to plan, deliver, operate and control services offered to customers²⁰.

Service and resource management plan: Overall plan for implementing and operating a service and resource management system (SMS).

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the European Union

Service and resource management system (SMS): Overall management system that controls and supports management of service and resources within an organisation or federation²¹.

Service and resource portfolio: Internal list that details all the service and resources offered by a service and resource provider, including those in preparation, live and discontinued²².

Service and resource provider: An organisation, a part of an organisation or a federation that manages and delivers services and resources to users/customers.

Service and resource report: Report that details the performance of a service and resource/resource versus the service and resource targets defined in service and resource level agreements (SLAs) – often based on key performance indicators (KPIs).

Service and resource request: A user request for information, advice and access to a service and resource.

Service and resource review: Periodic evaluation of the quality and performance of a service and resource together with the customer or under consideration of customer feedback, from which opportunities for improvement are identified, follow-up actions to increase the value of the service and resource are determined.

Service and resource target: Reference/target values for a parameter used to measure the performance of a service and resource, listed in a service and resource level agreement (SLA) related to this service and resource²³.

Thematic services: Scientific services (incl. data) that provide discipline-specific capabilities for researchers. (e.g. browsing and download data and apps, workflow development, execution, online analytics, result visualisation, sharing of result data, publications, applications).

Underpinning agreement (UA): Documented agreement between a service and resource provider and an external supplier that specifies the underpinning service and resource(s) or service and resource component(s) to be provided by the supplier, together with the related service and resource targets²⁴.

Underpinning contract (UC): See: Underpinning agreement (UA).